

VALIDATION OF THE MALNUTRITION UNIVERSAL SCREENING TOOL (MUST) IN HOSPITALIZED ACUTELY ILL ELDERLY PATIENTS IN PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Background and Objectives:

This study validated Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool (MUST) for the nutrition assessment of elderly patients against a reference tool- Patient Generated Subjective Global Assessment (PG-SGA).

Methods and Study Design:

70 patients admitted in the general wards were taken as sample in the study. In addition to MUST and PG-SGA certain other parameters were also checked; %weight loss, Triceps Skin Fold (TSF), Handgrip, Middle Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC) and Mid Arm Muscle Circumference (MAMC). Quality of life was checked by using EuroQol questionnaire. Specificity, sensitivity, positive and negative predictive values were calculated to validate MUST against PG-SGA.

Results:

When MUST is compared with PG-SGA, results calculated were sensitivity of 34.1% and specificity of 100% with the positive predictive value of 100% and negative predictive value of 85%. The MUST score had significant inverse correlation with body mass index, Triceps skinfold thickness and Mid-arm muscle circumference but not with Handgrip strength. Malnourished patients had worse quality of life score.

Conclusion:

This study shows that MUST can be used for elderly acutely malnourished patients. Weight loss is also validated and the results are comparable to MUST's results. By this we can predict the risk of malnutrition easily.

INTRODUCTION

Malnutrition is common in the elderly population and its prevalence depends upon the setting, ranging from 10-30% in the community, to as high as 70% in the acute care setting (Kubrak and Jensen 2007). Malnutrition, as the name indicates, stands for, poor provision of nutrition. This could be due to inappropriate intake of nutrients either macro or minor which are unable to meet the required amount to

function properly or because of some physiological problems in which our body is unable to absorb the nutrients and fail to transport them at required site. This problem leads to many severe issues such as stunting mainly in children and wasting in any age group. Malnutrition is a very common issue that is increasing with the passage of time in many under developed countries as well as in developed

ones, and Pakistan in on a frightening downward trajectory as regard of malnutrition. Almost 2.7 million of deaths in children are due to malnutrition in Pakistan. This issue is also prevailing in hospitalized patients and many factors are contributing in it such as; longer stay in hospital, increased risk of infections, unhygienic food of hospital, irritating behaviors of patients so that they are unable to eat and digest the nutrients properly. Most importantly, diagnosis is missed in hospitalized patients as the experts are un aware of basic screening tools and unavailability of those tools is another problem. Following is the list of screening tools that are used to determine malnutrition; Validated Malnutrition Screening and Assessment Tools: Comparison Guide, DETERMINE Checklist, Malnutrition Screening Tool (MST) ,Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA®), Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool (MUST), Nutrition Risk Screening (NRS-2002), Subjective Global Assessment (SGA), Seniors in the Community: Risk Evaluation for Eating and Nutrition (SCREEN©). Most commonly used tools are MUST and SGA.

Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool (MUST) is designed to determine the nutrition status of a person that was designed by British Association of Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition (BAPEN). This basically is a five-step procedure (Stratton et al. 2004) (Elia 2003). Step 1: Measure height and weight to get a BMI score using chart provided. If unable to obtain height and weight, use the alternative procedures shown in this guide. Step 2: Note percentage unplanned weight loss and score using tables provided. Step 3: Establish acute disease effect and score. Step 4: Add scores from steps 1, 2 and 3 together to obtain overall risk of malnutrition. Step 5: Use management guidelines and/or local policy to develop care plan.

The results of this procedure are calculated and interpreted as 0 = low risk, 1 = medium risk and above 2 = high risk of malnutrition (Scott 2008). This is the most common and the best way to assess the patients who are at the risk of malnourishment or are malnourished. So that positive actions could be taken to regain health. Another very popular tool among clinicians is Subjective Global Assessment. In this method nutrition assessment in based more on physical

examination and assessment than nutrition intake. Factors such as Muscle wasting, fluid retention and subcutaneous fat are basically examined. Results are categorized as well nourished (SGA A), moderately malnourished (SGA B) and severely malnourished (SGA C) (Detsky et al. 1987). The more recent and developed form of SGA is PG-SGA. PG-SGA stands for “Patient Generated Subjective Global Assessment”. In this method, we examine objectively; the percentage weight loss of a patient, any fluctuations in eating patterns, symptoms associated with disturbed gastrointestinal tract, physical activity and mobility, metabolic rate, stress rate and quality of life and checked the sensitivity and specificity with other nutrition assessment tools. For convenience, results are calculated as a score that ranges from 0 to 35 than the above-mentioned categories. It is easier to know the severity of malnourishment that has been undergone over the course of time. This study is actually based upon the validation of MUST with PG-SGA in acutely malnourished patients who are hospitalized and are of 50 or above 50 years old.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

To check the validity of Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool (MUST), a total of 70 hospitalized patients were enrolled for this study. From total 70 patients, 43 were females & 27 were males. The study was completed in duration from February 2018 to March 2018. Patients were randomly selected from General Medicine Wards, Specialized wards and surgical wards of different hospitals. The patients were recruited and screened, based on an inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were patients who were acutely ill and are of age \geq 50 years. And exclusion criteria were palliative patients and those residing outside Lahore and also those patients who were unable to give valid consent or are not willing to participate.

Procedure:

Written permission was obtained from different hospitals of Lahore including Sir Ganga Ram, Services and Mayo to carry out this study. Participants who were admitted to the Acute Medical and General Medicine units were identified and information about the study was

provided. Written information consent was obtained from all participants and legal guardians (if participants have dementia or cognitive impairment).

Data collection & measures:

A questionnaire was designed specifically for this study and was divided into different sections to obtain demographic, EuroQol EQ-5D 5L index, Charlson Comorbidity index, MUST and PG-SGA score. Demographic data, health and medical history was obtained from medical record and case notes. The demographic characteristics of patients were recorded as follow: age, gender and mobility at the time of admission. Clinical characteristics were recorded as: presently diagnosed disease, number of comorbidities. Anthropometric measurements were obtained, including weight, height, hand grip strength with a hand held dynamometer with dominant hand, mid-upper-arm-circumference (MUAC) was measured using a measuring tape at the midpoint between acromion process and olecranon process, TSF (Triceps skin fold thickness) was measured by using calibrated Harpenden skin-fold caliper on the right side and MAMC (Mid-arm muscle circumference) was determined by using the formula $MAMC = MUAC - (0.3142 \times TSF(\text{mm})) = \text{in cm}$ (Isenring et al. 2010). MUST score was evaluated using anthropometric measurements. The EuroQol EQ-5D 5 level (EQ-5D 5L) questionnaire was also completed by all participants to check their quality of life. The EuroQol EQ-5D 5L is a modified form of EuroQol EQ-5D 3L0. It was developed by the European based researchers for the purpose to construct a self-administered and simple questionnaire to provide knowledge about preferences of given health status (Kind 1996). This questionnaire included following five dimensions (mobility, self-care, usual activity, pain/discomfort, anxiety/depression) on five different levels: no problem, slight problem, moderate problem, severe problem and extreme problem. Then the resultant values were converted into values ranging from -0.208 to 1 by using the UK specific algorithm. Patient Generated Subjective Global Assessment (PG-SGA) score was evaluated and it includes seven criteria; weight, food intake, symptoms regarding disease, activity and functions over past few

months, disease and its relation to their nutritional requirements, metabolic demands and physical examination. For the purpose of PG-SGA rating each criterion was given in numbers. For example, WEIGHT: during past two weeks weight has: decreased (1), increased (0), no change (0). Charlson Comorbidity index to check life expectancy was calculated using online Charlson Comorbidity index calculator.

Data Analysis:

For data analysis, the softwares used were Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS. Anthropometric measurements were recorded into an excel sheet and BMI, Percentage Weight Loss, MUAC was calculated by using standardized formulas to evaluate MUST and PG-SGA score. Charlson Comorbidity and EuroQol EQ-5D 5L indexes were also recorded for analysis. Descriptive analysis (standard deviation) was performed for all the demographic variables using SPSS. Sensitivity, specificity and positive and negative predictive values were calculated using “cross tab” under descriptive analysis to determine the validity of MUST among hospitalized elderly general medical patients. Sensitivity was determined by the percentage of malnourished patients correctly identified and specificity of was determined by the percentage of well-nourished patients correctly identified by MUST. Independent Sample T-test was applied to check significance of MUST against PG-SGA. Predictive value (p-value) determined that the MUST accurately predicts the absence or presence of malnutrition, compared to PG-SGA. A receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve (Read et al. 2005) explicated relative areas under the curves (AUC) to further explain the validity of MUST against PG-SGA.

Ethical Considerations:

Ethical letter has been taken from Research Ethical Committee of University of South Asia under the IRB. No. USA-RW/DR/2023/04/064.

RESULTS:

The mean age of participants was 65.5 years (range 40-100, SD 12.7) with the majority with females (n=43, 61.4%). The mean of number of comorbidities was 2.7 (range=1-4, SD 1.0) and

mean Charlson Index was 3.1 (range=0-21, SD 2.7). Most of the patients (n=28, 40%) need some support to walk (stick or walking frame) and 22 (31.4%) were bed bound, while 20 (28.6%) were independent in mobility. Majority patients present were with a principal diagnosis of cardiac

problem (n=12, 17.1%) and respiratory problem (n=11, 15.7%), 7 (10%) were presenting accidental falls and 2 (2.9%) were with CNS issues, while 38 (54.3%) were suffering with other miscellaneous diseases majorly including edema and diabetes. (Table 1)

Table 1. Participant demographic, health and physical characteristics (n=70)

	Mean (range) (SD)
Demographic Characteristics	
Age (years)	65.5 (40-100) (12.7)
Gender (women), n (%)	43 (61.4)
Mobility, n (%)	
Independent	20 (28.6)
Stick	12 (17.1)
Walking frame	16 (22.9)
Bed bound	22 (31.4)
Health Characteristics	
Admission diagnosis, n (%)	
Respiratory disease	11 (15.7)
Cardiac problem	12 (17.1)
Falls	7 (10)
CNS disease	2 (2.9)
Others	38 (54.3)
No of co-morbidities	2.7 (1-4) (1.0)
Charlson index	3.1 (0-21) (2.7)
Physical assessments according to gender	
Weight, kg	
Men	74.4 (50-105) (13.0)
Women	66.6 (47-100) (11.9)
BMI, kg/m²	
Men	24.9 (15-35) (4.8)
Women	22.7 (14-40) (4.7)
Handgrip strength, kg	
Men	22.4 (0-78) (24.2)
Women	10.9 (0-38) (10.2)
Triceps skinfold thickness, mm	
Men	18.9 (4-43) (13.1)
Women	19.4 (2-40) (8.7)
Mid arm circumference, cm	
Men	27.8 (19-43) (5.4)
Women	27.4 (12-45) (5.4)
Mid arm muscle circumference, cm	
Men	21.9 (13.7-30.4) (3.6)
Women	21.3 (8.8-32.4) (4.3)
EQ-5D index	
Men	0.5 (-11-1) (0.4)
Women	0.4 (-11-1) (0.3)

PG-SGA: Patient Generated Subjective Global Assessment; **MUST:** Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool; **IQR:** inter quartile range; **EQ-5D:** European Quality of Life.

Table 2 describes that according to PG-SGA 4 (5.7%) were nourished and 66 (94.3%) were malnourished while MUST found 47 (67.1%) nourished and 23 (32.9%) malnourished. The median length of hospital stayed (LOS) was 2.0 and malnourished patients stayed 1.5 days more

than nourished patients with $p < 0.233$. EQ-5D 5L utility scores were lower in significantly malnourished patients with median 0.309 (IQR -11-1) while well-nourished patients scored higher with median 0.616 (IQR -11-1) while the $p = 0.117$

Table 2. Characteristics of nourished and malnourished patients

	Nourished	Malnourished	<i>p</i> value
PG-SGA, n (%)	4 (5.7)	66 (94.3)	
MUST, n (%)	47 (67.1)	23 (32.9)	
Length of Hospital stay (in days), median (IQR)	2.0 (1-8)	2.0 (1-9)	0.233
EQ-5D index, median (IQR)	0.6160 (-11-1)	0.3090 (-11-1)	0.117

PG-SGA: Patient Generated Subjective Global Assessment; MUST: Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool; IQR: inter quartile range; EQ-5D: European Quality of Life.

Table 3 shows that when MUST results when compared with PG-SGA results, showed that 23 patients were malnourished (true positive, at risk) while 4 where well nourished (true negative, not at risk). In contrast, no one was wrongly classified malnourished but 66 where wrongly classified as well nourished (false negative), despite being

identified as malnourished by PG-SGA. When compared with PG-SGA, MUST had a sensitivity of 34.1% and specificity of 100% with the positive predictive value of 100% and negative predictive value of 85%. ROC curve area 0.528 showed good agreement.

Table 3. Nutrition risk (MUST) compared with Nutrition status (PG-SGA)

PG-SGA	MUST		Total
	Positive (at risk)	Negative (not at risk)	
Malnourished	23(true positive)	43(false negative)	66
Well Nourished	0(false positive)	4(true negative)	4
Total	23	47	70

MUST: Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool; PG-SGA: Patient Generated Subjective Global Assessment.

Must Score (Area under curve)	0.528
Weight Loss Percent (Area under curve)	0.138

PG-SGA (Reference)

Figure 1. Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve Agreement between MUST and PG-SGA. ROC: Receiver Operating Characteristic; MUST: Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool; PGSGA: Patient-Generated Subjective Global Assessment

DISCUSSION:

This study shows the validity of MUST compared with a reference nutrition assessment using PG-SGA in acutely ill patients in medical wards of hospital. The MUST tool was very effective to identify patients who are at risk of malnutrition, compared with PG-SGA.

Many studies has shown MUST in comparison with PG-SGA in acutely ill patients with multiple comorbid illnesses. (Boléo-Tomé et al. 2012) compared MUST with PG-SGA in their study on cancer patients undergoing radiotherapy and show effective performance to identify patients at nutrition risk, including age range of 18-95 years.

(Stratton et al. 2004) in their study on hospitalized patients shown good agreement between MUST and SGA in newly admitted patients, while using SGA the investigator did

not categorize patients into malnourished group, but in our study this validity is not applied to PG-SGA results.

Despite adoption of guidelines to screen malnourish patients, under nutrition is neglected in hospitalized patients. It was expected that MUST was completed on all patients but actual rate of completion was zero. If malnutrition identification is missed then it becomes costly for hospitals as it is considered as complication under Australian refined diagnosis-related group (AR-DRG) classification system. (Gout et al. 2009) in their study on Australian hospitalized patients found only 15% correctly diagnosed malnourished patients with substantial shortfall to pay AUD \$1,850,540 in one financial year.

In study of (Kyle et al. 2006) in hospitalized patients found relation between increase length of stay (LOS) and increase MUST score risk. Along with them (Correia and Waitzberg 2003) in their study show longer length of stay in malnourished hospitalized patients with significant increase in costs for care of patients. MUST, unlike PG-SGA, is used by any trained professional without any expertise. Study found a significant weight loss in good relation with nutritional status with ROC area of 0.528 against PG-SGA. (Boléo-Tomé et al. 2012) in their cancer study concluded that weight loss is authentic nutrition parameter in comparison with PG-SGA to detect malnourishment. The weight loss parameter was not very important in the past and because patients may remain unknown about their weight. More research conducted to finalize weight loss as malnutrition marker and may be used to identify malnourishment, in mostly busy acute care where there is hesitance to perform screening tests.

Our study found QoL in hospitalized patients with a mean EQ-5D 5L score of men (0.5) and women (0.4). Well-nourished patients had significantly worse QoL in comparison with malnourished patients (median EQ-5D 5L scores: 0.6160 versus 0.3090). Our result did not match the study of (Rasheed and Woods 2014) on hospitalized patients have found low QoL with malnourished patients compared with well-nourished patients. Food has vital role for health and an inability to eat because of appetite loss, digestive or swallowing problems, affect QoL and these contribute to a low QoL in hospitalized patients.

This study uses MUST score and have diminished bias to score patients on PG-SGA component. This was the first study comparing MUST and PG-SGA among elderly hospitalized patients with multiple comorbid illnesses, as there are not so many studies on them. The limitation of this study is that it is unable to retain significant number of patients who had dementia or any impairment and also it did not include youngsters or those patients having specific organ defect. We admit that this study is limited to acutely ill elder patients, that just shows a portion of hospitalized patients and

these results are inapplicable to stable medical patients.

CONCLUSION:

This study shows MUST is a good screening tool in comparison with PG-SGA among elderly acutely ill patients and malnutrition screening is substandard in hospitalized patients leading to a number of patients being discharged without malnutrition diagnosis. This study shows that in contempt of developing hospital policies, MUST screening is suboptimal and this should be in notice because it causes division in terms of improved care quality. Further studies are proposed to confirm these conclusions and more efforts should be made for malnutrition screening in all the patients.

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